

Issues and Challenges of Demonetisation in India

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Abstract

This paper analyze about demonetization issues and challenges when it was implemented by the Govt of India. For every action there will be reaction. Demonetization was implemented on 500 and 1000 Indian currency notes. This article enumerates aftermath of demonetization in India. It answers to the following questions: - Was demonetization implemented at right time? Was demonetization good decision? Were People benefitted? For what Demonetization was implemented? Did the demonetization process reach the desired goal of the Government of India?

Keywords: Black Money, e-transactions, Employment, GDP, Fake currency

Introduction

India is developing country. Black money volume is also developing with India's economic growth. In India, Currency notes are used to do trade activities. People are taxed based on the type of business and income. A few people try to hide their income from paying tax to the Government. So black money volume rises. It reflects in Government Income. Government has to borrow loan from World Bank and issue treasury bills to raise funds for the people. 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 500, 1000 denominated currency notes were circulated before November 8, 2016. On November 8, 2016 the Prime Minister of India announced demonetization on 500 and 1000 currency notes. Indian People would not have expected this announcement in one night. They stood on queue in the bank to exchange demonetized currency notes (500, 1000) and tried to buy necessary items by exchanging banned currency notes. After implementation of demonetization many students might have searched meaning for it. Many people shouted and criticized the Government of India move. Demonetization had already been implemented two times (1946 and 1978) in India's history. Highly denominated currencies were removed and less denominated currencies were floated in the circulation.

Before getting in to the subject, everyone should understand the meaning of demonetization. Demonetization is removal of particular currency notes from the circulation. It is used to control inflation. Many business people welcomed the demonetization movement. A few economists opposed demonetization. Primary motive for implementing removal process of currency notes was curbing black money. After that many reasons were given from Government of India side. Vehicles were checked by the central and state uniformed

authorities. India is highly populated country next to China in the world. There are lakhs and lakhs of villages in India. Employees are in high numbers than the employers. Saving money is habit of many people in India. Buying Gold is also habit of many households. Banking facilities have not reached well in hamlet and tiny villages. People preserve money in their locker. Sudden announcement of demonetization devastated poor people. People were forced to exchange their invalid currency (500, 1000) within short period. Commercial banks and Cooperative banks were used to exchange the invalid currency notes at the time. A few people dead in the bank queue while standing to exchange the blocked currency notes. It did burst the argument in Television channels.

Issues and Challenges

Black Money

Black money means “the money hidden from the tax”. Black money is dangerous to one country’s economy. Politicians and Government Officers try to hide money earned from bribe. Business people try to hide their income from the business. Government of India tried to block black money. So it took demonetization decision. Demonetization will help to bring out black money from the tax evaders. But the question is, Did demonetization bring out black money? Answer is NO. GOI might have sent Income Tax authorities to these people houses and offices. If not, GOI might have passed an act which give severe punishment to the tax evaders and the people involving in bribe. Business People and Politicians used their power to exchange their black money. Now black money is stored in new denominated 2000 currency note and newly featured 500 currency note. Black money is stored not only in cash. It is also stored in the form of land, jewel and bonds. Though demonetization is good move, it will not only be helpful to control black money. Government should encourage the people and entities to use e-transactions.

Abolition of Fake Currency

Fake currency means replica of original. Circulation of Fake currency is most dangerous in the economy. Enemy countries and Terrorists are circulating fake currency in India. It affects bottom of the people. Fake currency notes are printed on highly denominated currency notes. If anyone is cheated with fake currency, he or she will have to lose the real income. Demonetization helped the Government of India to remove fake currency notes from the circulation. RBI printed new 500, 2000 denominated currency notes with high security features. Fake currency circulation has been controlled.

Due to technological development, Fake currency notes are being circulated in newly denominated currencies. To remove fake currency in permanent, Government should stop to circulate paper currency and encourage e-transactions.

E-Transactions

Government encourages e-transactions in all trade activities. Because fake currency can be abolished entirely by using e-transaction process. Moreover by using e-transaction facility bribe can also be controlled. Because e-transaction is done through banks. So transaction will be documented. Hence all income will come under the purview of income tax authorities. People began to send and receive money and pay bills through e-wallets like Paytm, Oxygen and banks authorized mobile applications after demonetization. But illiterate people are unable to use mobile applications and unaware about e-transactions. So the GOI may organize awareness programme on e-transactions. Many companies and Government entities should be brought into E-Transaction curb like Government buses, Electricity bill payment, Railways, Ration shops, Liquor shops, Hotels, Kirana Stores and Jewelry shops. Because currency notes are highly used in these type of entities.

Employment

After the implementation of demonetization, many organizations were unable to exchange their invalid currency notes in their hands. Employers had to deposit their cash in hand and withdrew the money in part and periodically. It affected daily and monthly salaried people who got their salary in hand. Employees were not given salary properly due to shortage of less denominated currency notes like 50,100. They were unable to buy needed items for their life. Demonetization highly affected daily wage laborers. Employees were sent on lay-offs. Due to this problem, business activities shrunk. It reflected in GDP.

Conclusion

Demonetization is good move. But it should have been informed earlier. Before implementing demonetization, the RBI and the Government should have kept less denominated currency note in high numbers. Demonetization highly recommended when inflation is not in control. Instead of demonetizing currencies, GOI might have used tax authorities to bring out black money and encouraged the people and business entities to use digital transactions. Demonetization will bring benefits only in long term. People cannot expect benefits in short period. Finally Demonetization is right decision at wrong time.

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